

Project partners

Join our Stakeholder
Replicability Board

7 organizations
5 countries

Project coordinator

IDENER RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT A.I.E

Earley Ovington, 24. Unit 8. 41300.
San José de la Rinconada (Sevilla, Spain)

Contact us

patricia.royo@idener.ai

arturo.sanchez@idener.ai

info@cooperant-project.eu

COOPERANT project

@cooperantproject

Zenodo: COOPERANT

Leading-edge
cooperative advances
towards the next
generation of
Concentrated Solar
Power (CSP) technology

Funded by
the European Union

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Objectives

- Design and demonstration of the COOPERANT CSP-TES, a technological innovation based on a high-performance open volumetric receiver.
- Coupled system with hybrid Thermal Energy Storage (TES) system working at very high temperatures (up to 1000 °C), that uses air as the Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF).
- Development of digital intelligence COOPERANT-AI TOOL for orchestrating CSP-TES coupling.
- Feasibility and scientific proof of short-term heat storage technology with demonstration at TRL4 (Technology Readiness Level).
- Holistic assessment of COOPERANT solutions' viability considering circularity, health, environment, social and economic impacts.
- Boosting adoption and further commercialisation through COOPERANT-TRANSFER.

COOPERANT innovations

COOPERANT CSP-TES PROTOTYPE

Development of a novel prototype with three main features:

1. High-performance Open Volumetric Receivers (OVR) for solar absorption and use of air as HTF
2. Thermal Energy Storage (TES) hybrid packed bed system
3. High-temperature solid-state mixtures and Phase Change Materials (PCM)

Impacts

Social Impact: COOPERANT increases acceptance of CSP, TES, and digital tools, provides public resources, and creates jobs to boost industry growth.

Environmental impact: The project improves CSP plant efficiency (>42%), reduces the environmental impact (>20% reduced footprint) and promotes sustainable value chains.

Scientific/Technological Impact: COOPERANT validates first-of-a-kind prototypes, creates breakthrough knowledge, and enhances EU leadership in renewable energy integration.

COOPERANT AI-TOOL

This Artificial Intelligence (AI) data-driven tool will monitor and couple the management of the flexible load TES with CSP generation.

It proposes advanced control based on:

1. Reinforced Deep Learning (rDL) technique to develop a Digital Twin (DT).
2. Multicriteria Design Optimization (MDO) to make informed decisions towards replicability.

COOPERANT TRANSFER

CIVIL SOCIETY

General Public, Young generations and students

ACADEMIA

Scientific community, PhDs & international experts

GOVERNMENT

Policy makers and Associations and clusters (P4Planet Made in Europe, Building4people)

ENVIRONMENT

Communicate circularity, environmental, economic and social benefits/impacts

INDUSTRY

Energy utilities seek reliable renewable power, industries need clean high-temperature heat, engineering firms work to integrate advanced technologies, and materials companies support the development of next-generation CSP and TES